

POLITICAL SCIENCE

Review

Vol. 14. No. 1, 2026

Published by:
Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria.

POLITICAL SCIENCE REVIEW

Vol. 14. No. 1, 2026

**A PUBLICATION OF THE DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL
SCIENCE, FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY
OF ILORIN, ILORIN NIGERIA**

E- ISSN 3121-9330

EDITORIAL BOARD

Editor-in-Chief

Professor H. A. Saliu

Editor

Dr. A. J. Edun

Associate Editor

Dr. A. A. Isiaq

Managing Editor

Dr. M. Ake

Editorial Advisers

Professor Alaba Ogunsanwo, University of Lagos

Professor Alex Gboyega, University of Ibadan

Professor Lere Amusan, North-West University, South Africa

Prof. E. O. Ojo, Department of Political Science, University of Ilorin,

Prof. A. J. Omede, University of Ilorin.

Department of Political Science, University of Ilorin

All Correspondence to: politicalsciencereview@unilorin.edu.ng

Disclaimer: The views and styles expressed in the articles in this publication are those of the individual authors and are not shared by the reviewers, the editors, the editorial consulting board, the Department of Political Science, or the University.

CALL FOR PAPERS POLITICAL SCIENCE REVIEW (PSR)

PSR is a peer-reviewed journal published twice in a year by the Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ilorin. Nigeria in June and December. The journal publishes articles, book reviews, commentary, briefings and debates on political issues, processes in Nigeria, Africa and the entire globe

The journal seeks to publish original empirical and theoretical research on policy relevant issues. Comparative Studies are equally welcome. The journal is intended to satisfy the academic needs of students, academic specialists, policy makers and general readers with focus on Nigeria and Africa within the context of sub-national, national, regional and international discourse. It seeks to expand the frontiers of knowledge and foster intellectual interaction among academics as well as policy makers.

EDITORIAL POLICY AND GUIDELINES FOR CONTRIBUTORS

The Editorial Board has no preference for any socio-political ideology or viewpoint. Authors are allowed to freely share their viewpoints as long as such views contribute to the understanding of political developments in Nigeria, Africa and the world. Copyright of contributions in the journal is automatically transferred to the Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ilorin, on acceptance for publication. However, the views expressed in the published contributions belong solely to the author(s) and not the Journal or Editorial Board.

Contributions submitted for consideration must not have been published previously or currently under consideration for possible publication elsewhere. Conference papers are welcome but the conference detail where such paper was presented must be duly acknowledged as footnote on the front page.

Contributions are invited from all over the world (in English language only). For the June edition, manuscripts must have been submitted not later than March 31st, while for the December edition, manuscripts must have been submitted not later than October 31st. Manuscripts should be submitted to:

The Editor

Political Science Review (PSR) Department of Political Science Faculty of Social Sciences University of Ilorin P.M.B. 1515, Ilorin, Nigeria

Soft copy should be sent as attachment in MS Word format to:
politicalsciencereview@unilorin.edu.ng

PROCEDURAL STAGES AND CONDITIONS OF PUBLICATIONS

Contributions for publication shall pass through three stages. Upon submit the manuscript will be subjected to in-house assessment by the Editorial Boa compliance with PSR policy and house style Authors whose papers are consider worthy for external blind review will be required to pay a non-refundable for of N10,000.00 (or equivalent in USS). The reports of the two reviews will be sent the authors) for corrections (if any). Authors of publishable manuscripts that attract positive decision from the reviewers will be required to pay a final publication of N20,000.00 (or its equivalent in USD). Author(s) of successful papers are entitled to a complimentary copy of the journal version where their papers appear.

CONTRIBUTION LENGTH

Articles should not exceed 8,000 words including references with an abstract of approximately 250 words with five keywords. Book reviews should be between 800 and 2,500 words, and must be accompanied with front cover scan of the reviewed book, scan of title page having the author(s), publisher, place of publication, date of publication, and ISBN Commentaries, Briefings and Debates on issues of development interests or critical explanation or policy analysis should be between 1,500 and 3,000 words.

PRESENTATION AND REFERENCE STYLES

Acronyms and Abbreviations should be written in full for the first time with acronyms and abbreviations in brackets. Quotations longer than three lines should be indented on both sides with no quotation marks. Double quotations marks should be used when quotations are less than three lines. Non-English words should he italicized. Referencing should strictly conform to APA style, 6th edition.

For further information, contact: The Editor, PSR, Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of florin. +2348030675617 OR: The Managing Editor +2347064275374.

NOTES ON CONTRIBUTORS

Professor Emmanuel O. Ojo, Department of Political Science, University of Ilorin, P.M.B. 1515, Ilorin, Kwara State.

Gbenga Owoeye (PhD), Department of Political Science and International Relations, Landmark University, Omu-Aran, Nigeria.

Samson Oluwole Babatunde, Department of Criminology and Security Studies, Thomas Adewumi University, Oko Irese, Nigeria.

Olufemi Adeola Toyinbo, Department of Criminology and Security Studies, Thomas Adewumi University, Oko Irese, Nigeria

Ameh Musa, Department of Criminology and Security Studies, Thomas Adewumi University, Oko Irese, Nigeria.

Olanrewaju Ajakaiye, Department of Mass Communication, Adeleke University, Ede, Nigeria.

Sani Ali, Department of Political Science, Bayero University, Kano

Akuandna Iliya Felix PhD, Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Jos, Jos-Nigeria.

Olaniru, Oluwatosin Shoyoye, The Polytechnic Ibadan. Public Administration Department, Ibadan.

Tajudeen Kaab Ayodeji, Centre for Peace and Security Studies, Al-Hikmah University Ilorin, Nigeria.

Dr. Zarat Uthman JP. FICMC, FADR, MSPSP, Centre for Peace and Security Studies Al-Hikmah University Ilorin, Nigeria.

Nurudeen Muhammad, Department of Political Science and Public Administration Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Edo State University Iyamho Edo State.

Ogbeide Frederick, PhD, &²Department of Political Science and Public Administration Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Edo State University Iyamho Edo State.

Sunday Evaristus Abonyi (PhD), Department of Social Work, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Samuel Abidemi IDOWU, Centre for Peace and Strategic Studies, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Abdussalam Abdulhameed, Centre for Peace and Strategic Studies, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

ABDULLAHI Alabi (PhD), Department of Politics and Governance, Kwara State University Malete-Nigeria.

Dr. IBRAHIM, O.Salawu. Department of Politics and Governance, Kwara State University Malete-Nigeria.

ABIOYE, Wasiu Olatunji, Department of Politics and Governance, Kwara State University, Malete-Nigeria.

Sanusi, Surajudeen Ishola, Department of Business Administration and Management, Kwara State Polytechnic, Ilorin.

Ganiyu Olanrewaju Issa, Department of Health Humanities and General Studies, Faculty of Health Humanities and Multi-Disciplinary Studies, Federal University of Health Sciences, Ila-Orangun, Osun State, Nigeria.

Oluwafemi Babatunde Oladimeji, Department of Political Science, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

Dr. Ibrahim Salawu, Abdulrahman Robiat Opeyemi; Department of Politics and Governance Kwara State University, Malete.

Solomon Selcap Dalung; LLM, LLB, BL, Solomon Dalung Foundation for National Unity, Abuja.

Vahyala Adamu Tari (PhD), Department of Political Science Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano.

DII, Christian Tsaro; Department of International Affairs & Diplomacy, Baze University, Abuja.

Olorunsuwa, Elijah Ola, Department of Political Science, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

Moses Danjuma, Bot, Department of Political Science, University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria.

Kajang Emmanuel Mindat, Department of Political Science, University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria.

Bitrus, David Itsegok, Department of Political Science, Nigeria Defense Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria.

Moshood Olayinka Salahu (PhD), Department of Politics and Governance, Kwara State University Malete, Nigeria.

Amin Amin (PhD); Department of Public Administration, Kwara State University Malete, Nigeria.

Shuaib, Olarewaju Moyosore, Department of Political Science, Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria.

Solomon, Adekunle Benjamin, Department of Political Science and Public Administration, Baze University- Abuja.

Suleiman Mohammed Basheer, Department of Political Science and Public Administrations, Baze University-Abuja

Sanusi Abdulwasiu (Ph.D.), Department of Social Studies Shehu Shagari College of Education (SSCOE) Sokoto.

Danyahaya Muhammad Shehu (Ph.D.), Department of History and International Studies Federal University Birni Kebbi.

Sa'idu Abdullahi, (Ph.D), Department of Political Science, Bayero University, Kano.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

The Media as A Political Resource in Nigeria: A Rear-View Mirror
Professor Emmanuel O. Ojo 1-22

Judicialisation of Party Primaries in the 2023 Nigerian General Elections:
Implications For Internal Party Democracy
**Gbenga Owoeye., | Samson Oluwole Babatunde., | Olufemi Adeola
Toyinbo., | Ameh Musa, | Olanrewaju Ajakaiye** 23-41

Reflections on the Political Thought of Niccolo Machiavelli
Sani Ali..... 42-61

Nigeria–Qatar Economic Diplomacy: LNG Cooperation and Investment
Opportunities In Energy Infrastructure
Akuandna Iliya Felix PhD..... 62-82

Electronic Voting: A Panacea for Good Governance and Electoral
Administration in Nigeria
Olaniru, Oluwatosin Shoyoye 83-99

National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) and Its Effectiveness in
Curbing Drug Abuse in Ilorin Metropolis
Tajudeen Kaab Ayodeji | Dr. Zarat Uthman JP. FICMC, FADR, MSPSP
..... 100-126

Democratic Governance and Vote Buying: Implication for Nigeria’s
Democracy (2015-2024)
Nurudeen Muhammad | Ogbeide Frederick, PhD 127-152

Democratic Governance and Social Welfare for Older Adults in Nigeria’s
Fourth Republic
**Sunday Evaristus Abonyi, | Samuel Abidemi Idowu | Abdussalam
Abdulhameed**..... 153-171

Employee Performance and Human Capital Politics in Public Tertiary
Institutions in Nigeria (A Study Of University of Ilorin, Ilorin and Benue State
University Markudi)

Dr. Abdullahi Alabi Dr. Ibrahim, O. Salawu. Abioye, Wasiu Olatunji Sanusi, Surajudeen Ishola	172-202
Endsars Protests Of 2020 in Nigeria: Unveiling the Issues and Implications on Governance	
Ganiyu Olanrewaju ISSA Oluwafemi Babatunde Oladimeji.....	203-225
Contested Affinities: France’s Soft Power Strategy and the Shifting Reception in Postcolonial Benin Republic	
Dr. Ibrahim Salawu Abdulrahaman Robiat Opeyemi.....	226-245
Alleged Christian Genocide and the U S’s Designation Of Nigeria As A ‘Country of Particular Concern’: A Legal Reflection And Its Implications for Nigeria and Africa	
Solomon Selcap Dalung, LLM, LLB, BL Vahyala Adamu Tari PhD....	246-269
Stunted Development Patterns in Africa: Culture or Colonial Past to Blame?	
DII, Christian Tsaro	270-307
Nature of Elections in Africa: A Review of Kenya and Zimbabwe Elections (2000-2020)	
Olorunsuwa, Elijah Ola Moses Danjuma, Bot Kajang Emmanuel Mindat Bitrus, David Itsegok.....	308-340
Institutional and Administrative Barriers to the Implementation of the National Health Insurance Authority (Nhia) Policy in Plateau State	
Moshood Olayinka Salahu (Phd) Amin Amin (PhD) Shuaib, Olarewaju Moyosore.....	341-362
E-governance and Public Service Delivery in Kuje Area Council, Abuja, Federal Capital Territory	
Solomon, Adekunle Benjamin.....	363-389
From Overload to Efficiency: A Qualitative Analysis of INEC’S Mandate and the Case for Unbundling	
Sanusi AbdulwasIU (Ph.D.) Danyahaya Muhammad Shehu (Ph.D.)	390-421

Adhering to Principles of Good Governance as A Panacea For Rising
Performance of Local Government In Nigeria

Sa'idu Abdullahi, Ph.D......422-455

Adhering to Principles of Good Governance as a Panacea for Rising Performance of Local Government in Nigeria

Sa'idu Abdullahi, Ph.D.

Department of Political Science, Bayero University, Kano
E-Mail Addresses: *asaidu027@gmail.com, asaidu36@yahoo.com*

Abstract

The paper aims to improve the local government's performance by adhering to the principles of good governance. Nigeria has experienced several underperforming local government systems. This led to various reforms of the local government system and increased funding for local governments. Despite this, local governments in Nigeria continue to underperform in improving the people's welfare. The paper relied on secondary data. Using Democratic-Participatory Theory (DPT). The paper emphasises that the performance of local governments in Nigeria can be improved only by adhering to the principles of good governance, which comprises three interrelated elements including accountability, transparency and citizens' participation in the affairs of local government administration. This becomes imperative because citizens' participation enhances accountability, which depends on how transparent and prudent local government officials are in managing public funds. The paper suggested that local people should be mobilised and educated to participate in their own affairs to improve governance. Above all, resources should be equitably distributed. The paper also recommended the strengthening of institutions established to fight corruption. Above all, the system of local government should be operated democratically.

Keywords: *Local Government, Development, Governance, Participation, Accountability*

Introduction

Local government administration has been an indispensable part of the state administration. The creation of local governments became necessary because other levels of government are tasked with performing enormous responsibilities. Therefore, adding the responsibility of local affairs to these two levels of government is likely to affect their general performance. Local governments are created not only to meet the demands of local people, but also to decongest the functions that other levels of government are expected to carry out (Salihi, 2001). The tasks performed by local administration depend on the demands and constitutional provisions imposed by the local circumstances, as well as the overall national development. This is a fact because for Nigeria to achieve its national development objective, the lives of its citizens residing in local communities must significantly improve.

The desire to improve local government's performance stems from its significant role in overall national development and in meeting the demands of the local people. Improvement in the living conditions of the rural populace is determined by the extent of the local government's performance. This can hardly be achieved without adhering to the principles of good governance. Enhancing governance requires the participation of the local people. It relates to public accountability, openness, and prudent spending of public funds. The absence of sound governance limits local governments' performance despite the unique tasks assigned to them. In other words, local governments in Nigeria have yet to bring about the desired sustainable development at the grassroots due to dismal performance. This is evidenced by the increasing incidence of poverty and misery, worsening social inequality, which likely to deepen frustration and social tension, capable of bringing abhorrence and animosity. According to the World Bank report in 2025 that poverty rate among non-urban population reached 75.5 percent (*The Punch*, May 4, 2025, para 1).

Adhering to the principles of governance, or what others call "good governance", at the local level should go a long way to improve the

performance of local governments. By improving their performance, it is hoped that the conditions of local people will improve significantly. This cannot be achieved without encouraging a system of local government that would promote justice, local people's participation, and improvement in their living conditions. Thus, when people are allowed to participate, accountability and openness are also ensured, which would likely improve the local government's performance. Accountability, participation, equality, and social justice are keys to good governance. Improving governance preconditions the increase in the performance of the local government, which will also facilitate sustainable development (Abdullahi & Ahmad, 2018).

The priority to improve local governments' performance led to several reforms and transformations in the local government system. The most prominent local government system reform was that of 1976 which produced a single tier of local government throughout the country (Dalhatu, 2008). It is worth noting that before the 1976 local government reform, several systems of local government administration existed. Despite several reforms and increased funding to improve local governments' performance, the living conditions of the local people continue to worsen as significant percentage of population have limited access to safe water, quality medical services, and formal education. There is no road network connection and sanitation. The underlying challenges which persist since the return of a democratically elected government in 1999, posing an imminent risk to national development.

This suggests that the government's actions and policies are insufficient to improve the performance of public institutions and governments (Wilson, 2000). This is a fact, particularly at the local level. The performance of the local government can only improve with adequate utilisation and equal distribution of resources among the citizens in line with public accountability and transparency in governance. Local people must be allowed to participate in affairs of their own government. In addition, the management of the resources at the local government level should be improved through prudent spending of

public funds. Addressing this would enhance the local government's performance. Accountability, transparency, and participation in the decision-making process constitute keys to good governance.

This paper attempts to examine the significance of adhering to the principles of good governance in improving the performance of local government in Nigeria. In doing so, the paper answers some pertinent questions about the socio-economic conditions of Nigerians at the grassroots level and what is needed to enhance the performance of local governments. This study addresses the need to improve the local government's performance by adhering to the principles of good governance.

The study is divided into six sections. Section One is the introduction, followed by a literature review and a conceptual explanation in Section Two. Section Three dealt with the theoretical explanation, and the discussion of the socio-economic situation of the local communities was in Section Four. Section Five discusses the need to adopt good governance and how it would raise local government's performance, and Section Six concludes.

Governance and Local Government: Literature Review and Conceptual Explanation

The difficulty of reaching a satisfactory and precise definition of the concept 'governance' has led many to provide a normative dimension of the concept (Wilson, 2000). Tracing the evolution of the concept, Wilson (2000) argues that the concept emerges in a specific historical context and has been utilised for a multitude of purposes. The desire for development among international organisations made governance more prominent globally. There is a relationship between the level of development and governance. However, since 1988, the focus of governance has gradually shifted from the development of global international organisations to management development, that is, how resources are utilised for human welfare.

By way of definition, Yaqub and Abubakar (2005) also define governance as the process of administering a political community. It encompasses the entire process of carrying out government activities to

transform the people's living standards. This involves the effective use of resources to ameliorate the developmental challenges and improve people's living conditions.

Bello-Iman (1997) considers governance as a mechanism in which an institution or organisation encourages participation of relevant interest groups in carrying out the responsibilities or tasks assigned to it. Such responsibilities are for the best interest of the group provides the basis upon which the institution or organisation is established. The institution or organisation is not only expected to perform but also to have an impact on human lives. This includes demonstrating the ability to mediate conflict among groups by means of distributing resources equally.

Ninalowo (2005) not only re-echoed the above conceptions of governance but also made a distinction between governance and government. To him, governance is the totality of administration and executive of the state to fulfil the contract it entered into between the state and citizens. It involves processes of government and management of the political community. On the other hand, the government referred to the management of state affairs. The actions of government, which are referred to as governance, are determined by the extent of commitment of those holding political positions. In a democratic system of government, where citizens elect those occupying political positions, the actions of government are expected to be geared towards satisfying the needs, aspirations, and welfare of the people. The people are expected to participate in the decision-making process as this ensures effective governance, particularly in a democratic setting.

Furthering this argument, Yaqub and Abubakar (2005) argue that the concept of governance is now recognised as "good governance", which signifies commitment to, and the ability to effectively address, allocate and manage resources in response to collective problems that confront society. Today, the majority of population in local government areas are still battling with the challenges of insecurity, poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, and many others lack access to basic social services that are

essential to make lives worthwhile. The word ‘governance’ is now also associated with democracy. Democratic governance is about governing people to enhance their welfare, attain their aspirations, and satisfy their needs with the limited resources available. There must be transparency and accountability in the use of societal resources to meet the demands and aspirations of the people. Hypothetically, societies under democratic governance are supposed to be ahead of those under autocratic rule in terms of infrastructural, social, and economic facilities to better the welfare of the citizens.

Deducing from the above, governance is about effective and efficient management of both human and material resources to meet the demands and aspirations of the people and transform their living conditions. This can be ensured through the participation of local people in their affairs and the equitable distribution of resources. Through participation, local people would be able to express their views on certain decisions that may likely affect their well-being. In addition, there should be transparency and accountability in the in dealing with public resources. Local government, according to Agbodike, Igbokwe, and Nkah (2014), is the substructure on which the superstructures of state and federal governments are founded. They further defined local government as a unit of administration with defined territory and powers, as well as administrative authority that is relatively autonomous. According to the 1976 local government reform, local government is:

Government at the local level is exercised through a representative council established by law to exercise specific powers within defined areas. These powers should give the council substantial control over local affairs as well as the staff and institutional and financial powers to initiate and direct the provision of services and to determine and implement projects to complement the activities of the state and federal government in their areas and to ensure, through devolution of functions to their councils and through the active participation of the people and traditional institutions, but that local initiative

and response to local needs and condition are minimised (FRN, 1976).

Ojo (1984) argued that local governments are created to provide local people with a superior capacity to understand and conduct their local affairs, as they are more acquainted with their locality than outsiders. Understanding their areas means they would contribute more to its development. Local people are believed to be closer to local government officials in meeting the local needs than the central government officials, who are far away. This is because each locality has its economic, social, and physical advantages and disadvantages. Each locality has its historical tradition and stage of social and economic evolution. Similarly, each locality has its way of life, beliefs, and orientations within the larger context of national culture. By this, each locality would develop significantly without affecting the other.

Ojo (1984) contended further that local government is created on the assumption that people are resistant to imposition from above. Any imposition of policies or programmes on the local people tends to be rejected when they are not involved. He further contends that the establishment of local government would uphold personal liberty and promote democracy, thereby preventing autocratic tyranny. Through this, the local government will provide an avenue for local participation in governance affairs. By establishing local administration, the welfare of those residing at the grassroots would improve through the provision of basic socio-economic services. This would ensure political socialisation, economic growth, and development in the local government areas.

Ganduje (2020) argued that local government is established to promote and advance the welfare of the common people. As the government gets closer to people, it becomes the real foundation for genuine grassroots development. He emphasises that, for local governments to be catalysts for economic growth and development, the managers of the affairs of local government should be aware that their primary responsibilities are to assist in controlling the masses, maintaining law and order, and

collecting all kinds of taxes and levies to execute more developmental projects at the grassroots level.

Adamu (2001, as cited in Dalhatu, 2008, p. 204) identifies three important reasons for establishing local governments. These are: to promote democratic participation, and to provide essential services that would bring development at the grassroots level by providing basic socio-economic services and infrastructure, such as quality healthcare, road networks, electricity, quality education, and safe water. The creation of local government gets government closer to the people. This is expected to promote participation in governance, which in the long run will enhance the local government's performance.

Adamu (2001, as cited in Dalhatu, 2008, p. 204) further notes that the local government systems should be considered as spaces for economic units, development areas, and political transformation. This means the essence of local government is broader. To achieve these objectives, local governments are tasked with specific functions. These functions of the local government are provided in Part IV, Section 27 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) and echoed by Dalhatu (2008, pp. 204-205). These functions include:

- a) The formulation of economic planning and development schemes for the Local Government Area;
- b) Collection of rates on radio and television licenses;
- c) Establishment and maintenance of cemeteries, burial grounds, and homes for the destitute;
- d) Licensing of bicycles, trucks, canoes, wheelbarrows, and carts;
- e) Establishment, maintenance, and regulation of slaughter houses, slaughter slabs, markets, motor parks, and public conveniences;
- f) Construction and maintenance of roads, streets, street lighting, drains, parks, gardens, open spaces, or such public facilities as may be prescribed from time to time by the House of Assembly of a State;

- g) Naming of roads, streets, and numbering of houses
- h) Provision and maintenance of public conveniences, sewages, and refuse disposal;
- i) Registration of all births, deaths, and marriages;
- j) Assessment of privately owned houses or tenements to levy such rates as may be prescribed by the Houses of Assembly of a State;
- k) Control and regulation of:
 - i. Outdoor advertising;
 - ii. Movement and keeping of pets of all descriptions;
 - iii. Shops and kiosks;
 - iv. Restaurants, bakeries, and other places for the sale of food to the public;
 - v. Laundries; and
 - vi. Licensing, regulation, and control of the sale of liquor

Other functions of local government identified by the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and re-echoed by Dalhatu (2008, pp. 205-206) are participation in the government of a state in respect to the following matters:

- a) The provision and maintenance of primary, adult, and vocational education facilities;
- b) The development of agriculture and natural resources, other than the exploration of minerals;
- c) Such other functions as may be conferred on a local government by the House of Assembly of a State.

Theoretical Explanation

This study adopts Democratic-Participatory Theory (DPT). Among the proponents of this theory is John Stuart Mill. His work on utilitarianism, liberty, and representative government emphasises the significance of representative government, which aims to promote good, reduce pain, and ensure liberty, equality, participation, and justice among people (cited in Gboyega, 1972). The thrust of the Theory is centred on the public good by protecting their fundamental human rights. It ensures justice and equitable distribution of resources among

individuals and groups, and guarantees their participation in the decision-making process. Participation, equal distribution of resources, accountability, and transparency are keys to improving governance.

The relevance of this theory is that a democratically elected local government council, as a representative council, is formed through election by the people. As democratically elected government authorities, local government councils have the responsibility to ensure that justice at the grassroots is achieved by guaranteeing substantial control over local affairs (Dalhatu, 2008). In the process of administering the local community, the participation of the local people is very significant. Thus, for effective and efficient local government administration, local people's participation should be encouraged. Participation in the decision-making process would enhance good governance and the local government's performance.

The theory also emphasises that to enhance governance at the local level, there should be justice and equality in the distribution of resources. Openness in governance and prudent spending of public funds should constitute a key to enhancing governance at the local level. This would prevent corruption and ensure accountability in governance. And where accountability is ensured, people's welfare is guaranteed.

Poor Socio-Economic Conditions of Local Communities

Undoubtedly, Nigeria is one of the richest countries in Africa. It has abundant resources, arable land, and a labour force. About 70 per cent of Nigerians reside in rural communities (Multidimensional Poverty Index, 2022, p. xiv). The majority are engaged in agriculture and agro-processing as their main economic activities. To ensure the needs of local people are adequately protected, local governments also receive their allocation from the federal account. The amount of funds allocated to the local government since 1999 is enormous. From May 1999 to June 2017, a total sum of 16 trillion naira was received by the existing 774 local governments to carry out their constitutional responsibilities. For instance, the South East, with the limited local governments (95), received 1,874,488,315,795.67 trillion Naira. The North West, with 186

local governments, received 3,952,786,225,360.97 trillion Naira (see Table below 1.1).

Table 1.1: Net Allocation and Local Government Areas by Region

Region	Local Government Areas	Total Amount Received (N)
North Central	121	2,667,833,695,846.51
North East	112	2,439,907,829,738.46
North West	186	3,952,786,225,360.97
South East	95	1,874,488,315,795.67
South South	123	2,478,214,447,974.37
South West	137	3,077,513,646,210.77
	774	16,490,744,160,926.70

Source: <https://www.slideshare.net>

Even though the federal allocation to local governments fluctuates, they continue to receive a significant portion of funds from the federal government. For instance, the International Centre for Investigative Report revealed that between January 2022 and June 2024, a total of 6.92 trillion Naira was disbursed to 774 local governments (ICIR, 2024, para 2). Table 1.2 shows that 2.62 trillion Naira was disbursed in 2022. This is higher than the amount allocated in 2023, which was 2.60 trillion Naira. Since the removal of the subsidy by President Ahmed Tenebu in May 2023, more allocations have been made to the local governments in Nigeria. Between June 2023 and June 2024, the sum of 3.34 trillion Naira was disbursed (ICIR, 2024, para 5). Similarly, several reforms were carried out to curb the myriad of challenges confronting the local government and improve its performance. These

reforms include the 1976 Local Government, the Dasuki reform, and many others.

Table 1.2: Monthly Allocation to Local Government Areas from the Federal Account

Month	Amount Disbursed in 2024 in Billion Naira	Amount Disbursed in 2023 in Billion Naira	Amount Disbursed in 2022 in Billion Naira
January	288.93	221.81	163.88
February	278.04	183.23	131.88
March	267.15	173.94	122.38
April	288.69	171.26	167.91
May	293.82	213.67	149.25
June	282.48	221.79	175.94
July	-	218.06	182.33
August	-	236.23	210.62
September	-	266.54	164.25
October	-	210.90	172.78
November	-	225.21	177.09
December	-	258.81	202.49
Total	1.69 Trillion Naira	2.61 Trillion Naira	2.62 Trillion Naira

Source: ICIR, 2024, <https://www.icirnigeria.org/how-much-was-disbursed-to-local-governments-in-three-years>.

Despite these reforms and the funds allocated to the local governments, their performance remains minimal. This has hurt the living conditions of the local people. There is nothing to write about the quality of healthcare provided to the local people. A significant number of them have no access to safe water and environmental sanitation. For instance, it was estimated that between 1990 and 1999, only 32 per cent of the local people had access to adequate sanitation. In addition, only 39 per cent have access to safe water, and illiteracy continues to gain ground due to a lack of quality education or even the absence of schools.

This is terrible for employment opportunities. According to the 2006 report of the Central Bank of Nigeria's Annual Statement of Account (2007), an estimated 31.9 per cent of people in urban areas, and 30.3 per cent in rural areas, who fall between the ages of 15 and 25, were employed. This means that an estimated 69.7 per cent of people residing in the grassroots, as compared with 68.1 per cent of urban residents, are roaming the streets without jobs (cited in Olowonini & Audu, 2012, p. 430).

By 2003, the percentage of unemployed graduates in local areas stood at 8.3 per cent. This is less than the rate of urban unemployed graduates, which stood at 17.3 per cent. By 2010, the urban growth rate of graduate unemployment had sharply risen to 22.8 per cent, and was lower compared with that of graduate unemployed people from local areas, which stood at 20.7 per cent. By 2011, urban graduate unemployment declined steadily to 17.1 per cent, while those from local communities rose significantly to about 25.6 per cent (Eneji, Mai-Lafiya & Weiping, 2013, p. 155). By 2022, the rural unemployment stood at 34.5 per cent. Rural underemployment rate was 26.9 per cent (Multidimensional Poverty Index, 2022, p.8).

Similarly, according to the 2022 report on the Multi-dimensional Poverty Index in Nigeria, about 63 per cent of Nigerians, or close to 133 million people, are multidimensionally poor. This is more common in local communities, where 72 per cent of the inhabitants are multi-

dimensionally poor, compared to 42 per cent of the urban population. It was estimated that 70 per cent of Nigerians residing in local areas, and roughly 80 per cent of the total people in those areas, are poor. The intensity of rural poverty stood at 42 per cent compared to 37 per cent in urban areas (Multi-dimensional Poverty Index, 2022, p. xiv).

Child poverty is also prevalent in the local countries, with almost 90 per cent of the children experiencing poverty (Multidimensional Poverty Index, 2022, p. xvi). This drastically reduced the per capita income in rural communities and inevitably deepened poverty. Thus, the high out-of-pocket expenditure contributed significantly to rising inequality in Nigerian rural communities, as those with higher incomes have access to quality education and food with high nutritional content than those with lower incomes.

Even though healthcare remains generally poor in the country due to weak health systems and socio-economic factors, access to healthcare services is more difficult for local inhabitants, largely because of their lower income and the government's inability to provide well-equipped hospitals. Many also lack access to proper sanitation facilities. Most rural hospitals are primary health centres. And where comprehensive hospitals are made available, many are lacking qualified medical personnel, modern medical equipment, and a hygienic environment. These prevent them from performing credibly in terms of providing the most needed service as expected. This imposes constraints on improving people's living conditions. The sluggish nature of local economies deepens insecurity and worsens poverty to 75.5 per cent in 2024 (*Guardian*, May 4, 2025).

Improving the Performance of Local Government: What are the Indispensable Elements?

To enhance the performance of government at the local level, there should be a system of government with well-functioning institutions and structures tasked with the enormous responsibility of ensuring the positive transformation of people's living standards at the grassroots. The system of government shall be democratically guided, where

people's representatives should oversee the affairs of local communities. This would guarantee them the power to control the elected officials. This would warrant the participation of the local people in the decision-making process. Once such power is commandeered elsewhere, it means the will of the people cannot be determined by them, and likely their participation would also be limited. The moment their participation is limited, it affects the ability to manage resources more effectively and deepens corruption among local government officials. This is because resources would be wrongly allocated, and for personal interests. Thus, a veritable democratic system of government is indispensable to improving governance at the local level.

Thus, the lack of a valid democratic system of government at the local level supports corruption and embezzlement of public funds. Corruption can limit local government performance. The presence of democracy, therefore, is a prerequisite for good governance. This would ensure the emergence of true representatives who would prioritise the local people's needs over those of personal interests. Through this, the welfare of the people will be catered to providing essential services for development. Such services include: potable water, quality healthcare, education, poverty reduction, road construction, and employment opportunities.

Democratising the system of government at the local level would further tie the contractual relationship between the government and the governed, which must be fulfilled. The provisions of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria deliberately established local government as a third tier of government, to fulfil this contractual agreement. Part of this is to satisfy the needs, interests, and aspirations of the people living in the local areas. However, this is yet to bring the desired result due to the absence of veritable good democratic governance. The local people are often not involved in the decision-making. Even if decisions are made by their so-called representatives, they are not being informed or aware of their existence. Thus, one can say that citizens' participation in governance is low, and if it exists at

all, it is just pseudo-participation. To improve the local government's performance, citizens must be encouraged to participate. Thus, participation of the local people is paramount and can enhance the performance of the local government.

Thus, because of the relevance of local people's participation in the administration of the local government, the existence of a favourable ecosystem for the local people to participate in the government's affairs is of the utmost importance. Educating and mobilising the local people would significantly provide a favourable environment for their participation. This is because education would make local people conscious of what is happening in their community. In addition, improving the welfare and living conditions of people at the grassroots is sufficient to encourage full participation of local people in governance affairs. This is because they are satisfied with what Maslow (1908-1970) called the basic human needs, such as food, shelter, and clothes.

There is a relationship between rising corruption and poor governance in the local government. Over the years, local governments in Nigeria have been battling with this challenge as both elected and non-elected officials have been found wanting. This means that those overseeing the affairs of the local government do not take into cognisance the principles of accountability and transparency. To ensure governance at the local government level, concerted efforts should be made to reduce corruption among elected and non-elected local government officials. This will go a long way in improving governance at the local government level. Thus, transparency and accountability should not only serve as guiding principles for those administering the local government but also as a yardstick for measuring its performance.

Lack of openness and accountability can likely bring about loss of the most needed resources for development at the local level. Therefore, people should have the political capacity to hold their representatives accountable for any actions or inactions. It can be hypothetically argued

that there is a close relationship between the level of development and the extent to which resources are managed at the local level. Put differently, the extent of development at the local level is determined by the commitment of those responsible for managing the local government's resources. Prudent and adequate utilisation of the limited resources available to the local government enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of resource management. This ensures an increase in the local government's performance.

Conclusion

From the discussion above, it has been noted that local governments are established to carry out local functions to better the condition of the local people. Several efforts were made by successful governments, both military and civilian, to improve the local government performance to transform the living conditions of local people. Yet their performance has had little, as the people's living conditions have not significantly improved due to poor governance. Improving governance at the local level would not only enhance the local government's performance but also improve the living conditions of the local people. With this, the paper recommends the following:

Since the provision under Section 7 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) recognises that local government is the formal governance mechanism through which democratically representative councils confirm laws and have substantial power to exercise control over local affairs, a veritable democratic system of government should be nurtured for the operation of local government in Nigeria. The election of public officials at the local government level should be given to an independent electoral management body. This would reduce the influence of state governors who only have their anointed boys elected into the local government councils.

Local government, as a third tier of government, should operate independently of other levels of government, both financially and

politically. However, the mandate to control the local government affairs should be a responsibility of the people themselves. The power to control their representatives should be strengthened constitutionally. Deliberate strategies should be in place to educate and mobilise local people to participate in the administration of their community. Their participation in the decision-making is paramount. Through participation, local people would be able to voice their problems. Educating the local people would make them aware of their rights over their representatives. This would help to improve governance; as such, more schools should be established to educate the local people.

Political leaders should be committed and sincere towards the development of the local community by providing quality healthcare, potable water, and a hygienic environment for the local people. Concerted efforts should be made to reduce corruption among local government officials. This is by strengthening the power of institutions set up purposely to fight corruption. This would help enhance the local government's performance for the betterment of the people.

References

- Abdullahi, A., & Ahmad, S. (2018). Good governance and local government administration in Nigeria: An imperative for sustainable development. In *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*. (pp. 1522-1532), Vol. 7, No.4. www.isdsnet.com/ijds.
- Agbodike, F. C., Igbokwe-Ibeto, C. J., & Nkah, B. C. (2014). Local government administration and the challenges of sustainable development in Nigeria. In *Review of Public Administration and Management*, (95-105). Vol. 3, No. 6. https://www.arabianjbmr.com/RPAM_index.php.
- Bello-Iman, B. I. (1997). Governance and development in Nigeria". In: I. B. Bello-Iman (ed). *Governance in Nigeria: Economy, Politics and Society in the Adjustment Years 1985-1995*. (pp.1-12). Ibadan, Stirling-Horden Publisher.

- Dalhatu, S. (2008). The local government system and the quest for sustainable development in Nigeria. In: Shehu Dalhatu (ed). *Issues on sustainable development in Nigerian local governments* (pp.200-211). Kano, Nigeria, Spider Web Publishing Company.
- Eneji, M. A., Mai-Lafia, D., & Weiping, S. (2013). Socio-economic impact of graduate unemployment on Nigeria and Vision 20: 2020. In: *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, (148 – 176). Vol. 2, No.1. www.isdnet.com/ijds.
- Federal Government of Nigeria (1976). Guidelines for local government reform. Publication of the Federal Government of Nigeria, Kaduna Government Printer.
- Ganduje, U. A. (2020). *Democracy and local government administration in Nigeria*. Lagos, Nigeria, Spectrum Books Limited.
- Guardian (2025, May 4). <https://guardian.ng>.
- ICIR (2024). How much did the FG disburse to local governments in the last three years? <https://www.icirnigeria.org/how-much-was-disbursed-to-local-governments-in-three-years>.
- Kinyata, S. G. & Abiodun, L. N. (2020). The impact of community participation on project success in Africa: A bottom-up approach. In: *International Journal of Research in Sociology and Anthropology* (IJRSA), (1 – 8). Vol. 6, Issue 3. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2454-8677.0603001>.
- Ninalowo, M.A. (2005). Antinomies of corruption and democratic governance. In: Lai Olurode and S. O. Akinboye (eds). *Democracy, good governance, and corruption in Nigeria: 1999-2005*. (pp.27-44). Lagos, Nigeria, Frankad Publisher.
- Olowononi, D. G. & Audu, I. (2012). Unemployment, national security, and sustainable development. In: A. R. Dunmoye, A. E. Unobe and R. A. Sanusi (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ABU@50 Humanities' International Conference*, (pp. 424-436). Zaria, Nigeria: Ahmadu Bello University.

Salihi, H. (2001). Local government as the third tier of government in Nigeria: Fact or farce?" In: *The proceeding faculty seminar series*, (pp. 46-84). Kano-Nigeria, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Bayero University, Vol. 1.

The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended).

The Punch, May 4 (2025). Poverty rate among rural Nigerians now 75%. <https://punchng.com>.

Wilson, H. R. (2000). Understanding local government: An international perspective. In *Revista de Administracao de Empresas/EAESP/FGV*. (pp.51-63). Sao Paulo, Brazil.

Yaqub, O. N. and Abubakar, O. S. (2005). "Conceptualizing good governance, corruption, and democracy". In: Lai Olurode and S. O. Akinboye (eds). *Democracy, good governance, and corruption in Nigeria: 1999-2005*. (pp.15-26). Lagos, Nigeria, Frankad Publisher.